

Philosophical Aspects of Library Studies

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ABSTRACT: The scientific-theoretical basis of the library science methodology is made up of world philosophy, logical science, special library science laws and principles aimed at the process of understanding. Also, librarianship widely benefits from the laws and principles of sociology in solving its theoretical and practical issues. Accurate definition of the scientific-theoretical bases of the methodology of librarianship is of great importance for its formation as a science, solving the problems of library work, and making serious scientific generalizations. It is impossible to develop strict scientific laws, principles and recommendations without scientific methodology.

Scientific methodology allows librarianship to be free from all uncertainties, unfounded assumptions and scientific errors. Thus, one cannot talk about the development of modern librarianship as a science without having a scientific methodology.

Librarians, theoreticians of library work should use the rules, principles and norms of the methodology when solving non-standard, complex librarianship problems, and draw their scientific conclusions and recommendations based on it. In other words, librarians should directly base their scientific conclusions and recommendations on methodology. Therefore, conducting high scientific research requires librarians to be based on both professional librarianship knowledge and philosophical, logical and sociological knowledge. Thus, the understanding of librarianship as both philosophical, logical and sociological, as well as special librarianship, gives rise to a general and special methodology. Conducting high scientific research requires librarians to be based on both professional librarianship knowledge and philosophical, logical and sociological knowledge. Thus, the understanding of librarianship as both philosophical, logical and sociological, as well as special librarianship, gives rise to a general and special methodology.

KEYWORDS: philosophy, library science, philosophical methods, general methodology, scientific methodology.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 20th century, especially in the second half of the century, great achievements were made in the organization of librarianship research. The formation and development of librarianship as a humanitarian science, the further strengthening of its relationship with other sciences, the use of research methods and methods of fundamental sciences gave it the opportunity to study and summarize the work experience of libraries with modern scientific methods and methods. Serious scientific-research works were started on various fields of librarianship: the formation of library funds, the creation of information and information systems of libraries, various forms and methods of the process of organizing service work for readers, the social functions of libraries, and the forms of librarianship research. (Xələfov, 2014). The participation of sociologists, psychologists, pedagogues, and informants, along with librarian specialists, in such research greatly contributes to the scientific solution of more serious tasks. Summarizing the results of the research and applying them to library work has greatly increased the efficiency of library service to readers by creating conditions for building library work on scientific bases.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In modern times, librarianship research is faced with very important tasks. It is necessary to devote such research directly to the solution of the tasks set in the field of the development of society, culture, science, education, formation and training of people, raising their cultural, intellectual and professional levels, delivering the achievements of scientific and technical progress to the masses. Modern library-information science is based on methodological and philosophical foundations needs and tries to be based on the objective laws of world development, which opens wide opportunities for library-information activities. Philosophical issues are not abstract and distant from the reality of libraries and information. Rather, it grows out of the characteristics of the library space. In recent years, the strengthening of interest in philosophical knowledge is more related to the transformations related to the formation of a unified knowledge space based on the network infrastructure in the conditions of the formation and

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development of the modern digital economy that develops and corresponds to it, moves towards the goals and tasks of the developing information society, and transforms our society into constantly improving digital technologies and it leads to a society built on knowledge where new ones emerge (knowledge society). The library and information industry is called upon to solve two types of problems. On the one hand, there are applied ones that require practical knowledge previously acquired through theoretical abstraction or evaluation of previous successful work experience. (Əhmədov, 2003). On the other hand, there are problems that do not yet have a proven and tested solution algorithm. To develop it, it is necessary to attract theoretical and philosophical knowledge. This group of tasks puts the question of the role of the library and the library-information industry in the knowledge society on the social and professional agenda and requires the development of a fundamental model of their long-term innovative development in the digital economy. Along with the search for knowledge, there are also processes of institutionalization of philosophical knowledge. The discussion of philosophical issues related to the library and information industry is reflected in the pages of prestigious professional publications such as "Scientific and technical libraries", "Library studies", "Bibliography studies". Consideration of separate aspects of this problem activates the internal dynamics of the discussion and brings new, previously unraised questions to the fore. According to scientists, tradition is "actually an amazing event that creates the entire culture and spiritual life of mankind, through which the content of thought, action, creativity, as well as feeling can be further transmitted as a material object by its original bearer and by". (The human dimensions of the library as a social institution and library-information activity are mostly determined by the preconditions of the professional society and its commitment to the traditions whose sources are the national book culture.

A. V. Sokolov is sure that bookmaking in the historical context ensured the preservation of the intellectual energy of society and contributed to the development of civilization. Tradition protects libraries, library-information activities and the professional community in times of crisis. The unity of traditions and innovations allows to develop the library field, to modernize the library and information industry without destroying its cultural basis and specificity. The philosophy of librarianship as a scientific-philosophical discipline performs a number of functions in a state of constant heuristic search. The analysis of A. V. Sokolov's publications shows the existence of worldview, ontological, epistemological, methodological and axiological functions. The cultural meanings and values of the philosophy of librarianship are inseparable from the worldview. The meanings and values of book culture, which have gone through a long history of formation and development, influence the strategies, vectors and horizons of the worldview of the professional community. It defines the ideological guidelines that are important in the work activities of industrial professionals. The philosophy of librarianship, realizing the ideological function, develops the system of views of the world and library specialists as an integral segment of social life. The ontological function is aimed at determining the essence, foundations, properties and principles of development of the philosophy of library science, as well as determining its place in the scientific landscape of the world. The epistemological function of the philosophy of librarianship is to determine the incompleteness and one-sidedness of previously received information about the philosophy of librarianship, to obtain new, justified, reliable, reliable and verifiable information about it as a segment of social life that requires philosophical understanding. The epistemological function manifests itself most clearly in the conditions of the formation of a unified knowledge space. The philosophy of librarianship is called upon to systematize the accumulated and developing cognitive fund about the empirical and theoretical levels of the library field and its diversity, helping to form a humane attitude in the professional society. The axiological function of the philosophy of librarianship is to seek harmony (at least balance) between the library-information activity and its socio-ethical assessment by the professional community and society as a whole. The axiological function permeates both practical and scientific activities of specialists working in various segments of the library field. Questions about the nature of the library as a social institution, its functionality and development trajectory, main directions of activity and their process components carry a value burden. According to A.V. Sokolov, it lays the foundation for the development of conceptual, cognitive-theoretical and logical-methodological structures necessary for understanding and forming a rational view as a cognitive search system that has internal semantic harmony and is constantly in motion.

3. METHODS

Methodology is the system of the most general primary, basic principles and methods of cognition, organization and construction of theoretical activity, as well as the doctrine of this system. Methodology studies laws, regularities, principles, cognitive functions, classification of species, research methods, scientific approaches and concepts.

Methodology of library science: this is a field of library science that studies the principles, functions, ways of knowledge of library science, develops theories, general and special methods of scientific library research, and approaches to the study of various objects of librarianship. Library science methodology is based on three principles.

Philosophical foundations of knowledge, especially about epistemology, which develops universal laws of knowledge about the world and surrounding reality:

For example, the law of the transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes. The law of "negation of negation" (or "spiral development") - this means that "everything has already happened", we just learn it at a higher level, take it. The law of unity and

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struggle of opposites (when development occurs as a result of conflict). (Dick, 1991). That science of "logic" should be based on the basic laws of all scientific theories and research (for example, the construction of classifications). The philosophy of librarianship is understood not as an integral, systematically organized structure, but as a set of guiding principles of library activity and theoretical provisions explaining library phenomena. The systemic crisis, which is a combination of economic, socio-political and axiological crises, greatly increases the importance of the conceptual and theoretical analysis of the extreme and optimal conditions of the existence of the "library" socio-cultural institution. Today, there is an increasing number of library professionals, both theorists and practitioners, who are interested in the philosophical aspects of librarianship. It is no coincidence that this trend was especially noticeable in the 90s of the 20th century, and further developed and strengthened in the future. The dynamics of socio-cultural changes taking place in the world confront libraries with the need to understand their new role in public life, define a new position in the hierarchy of information and cultural values of society, and develop modern ideological and methodological approaches. The library is located in the context of the moral and ethical norms that always prevail in the society as a public institution that has the character of value and has a direct and indirect influence on the formation of the personality. This means that the ethical self-determination of the library community, which is very relevant today, is formed under the influence of axiological (value) attitudes determined by a number of factors, among which are the megatrends of the postmodern period of modern literature. This period is characterized by negative trends in the development of modern civilization, a permanent socio-economic crisis for many countries of the world, the loss or transformation of leaders and values in the system of human relations, in the relations between society and people. Today, philosophers talk about such a phenomenon as sociocultural modernization, which means the formation of new normative value systems and meanings, as well as patterns of behavior. Changes affect all social systems to a greater or lesser degree, especially in the context of globalization and the emergence of many important social processes at the international level. The postmodern era poses many threats to the library as a social institution. All the unique programs they offer to get out of the crisis are united by a common moral basis. The ability to cope with all the diversity of approaches is associated with rationality, humanistic traditions and the spiritual capabilities of humanity. Therefore, in the process of eliminating the causes and consequences of the social crisis, the organic evolution of the value system and value management is of particular importance. At the same time, only with the conscious development of a person's spiritual culture and his abilities, it is possible to achieve changes in our world aimed at material values, to use the great cultural potential for higher spiritual purposes. The peculiarity of the "Library" state institution is that, unlike other information repositories, it has the ability to perform a value-oriented function in society. (Butler, 1933). Forming its collections according to the axiological paradigm of society, the library acts as a creator of a new cognitive-ethical reality that has the ability to influence the world of people and documents. However, in order to successfully perform this function, it must have its own concept and philosophy based on the system, that is, the "national idea" of the society that is historically unique to it and interpreted from the perspective of the current state ideology, capable of resisting the destructive tendencies of postmodernism, must be formed. On this basis, the main directions of the library's activity will be determined.

As a final model, technological and serious transformational changes in experimental librarianship, as well as new knowledge in the field of functional aspects of the library, began to form. Currently, the process of deepening scientific knowledge in the field of determining the library status and the essence of its composition is underway, several approaches are emerging. If libraries are formed on the basis of this process, then at the end of scientific results, libraries enter the status of ideological and technological institutes. Such a scientific approach allows to analyze the library activity from the point of view of content, the essence of its composition, and the reality of resources. (Shera, 1965). Characteristics of the library fund; categorical services fundamentally affect the methods of learning library informatics and reveal the parameters of electronic librarianship.

The approach from the position of special librarianship provides an opportunity to apply the economic aspects of library technology in library service. If library activity is viewed as an institution that creates and distributes library products to the public, then the basic concept of libraries is paradigmatic.

4. CONCLUSION

They are considered as an economic entity that actively participates in the formation of the social structure according to the number and level of the population of any area. In the conditions of qualitative changes, a new approach to experimental library science and library science has been introduced with management, marketing and technological model in researches in the field of library science and real library activity. This approach affects the approach of library science to the background of science. The philosophy of librarianship and the manifestation of electronic librarianship further value the formation of this model.

In the early 2000s, library products and library activities created in the socio-economic environment, as well as the essence of internal and external facts, were more thoroughly studied by the representatives of the scientific school of librarianship. This makes it possible to draw the conceptual framework of library activity as a special direction of librarianship knowledge, but the characterization of its object and subject was formed as a science in the second half of the 20th century.

Strengthening the status of library science as a science and knowledge is a requirement of the information society. So, a librarian specialist should penetrate into science in order to mature theoretically.

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From what has been said, we can conclude that librarianship can come to the background of scientific studies in the aspect of researching deep scientific and theoretical knowledge that combines scientifically formed knowledge and brings new successes to the library reality.

Thus, the methodological importance of the philosophical approach in the science of librarianship for librarianship is that librarianship based on this premise has the opportunity to study the past, understand modernity, think about the future, and make predictions. In improving the scientific-philosophical essence of librarianship, the principles of great importance as the categories of philosophy play the role of a rich scientific methodological base.

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